

Degradation of Reed's Base and Combes' Base

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Synthesis of 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro derivatives of Reed's base and its complete degradation to 2-amino-1-naphthoic acid are described. Similarly synthesis of 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-2,4-dimethyl-6,7-benzoquinoline (Combes' base) and its complete degradation to 2-amino-3-naphthoic acid is also described. This constitutes an evidence that Reed's base is angular while Combes' base is linear.

Experimental

All m.ps are uncorrected, ir spectra was taken in KBr disc.

1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-2,4-dimethyl-5,6-benzoquinoline (II): To 2,4-dimethyl-5,6-benzoquinoline (2 g) 60 ml conc HCl was added, warmed and 7 g tin foil was added portionwise. The mixture was heated on water bath for one hour and left overnight. The separated colourless mass was filtered and suspended in water. It was made alkaline with NaOH solution and extracted with ether. The base obtained on evaporation of ether was recrystallised from petroleum ether (60-80°); colourless needles m.p. 109-10° soluble in methanol, chloroform and acetone but insoluble in ethyl acetate. Found: C, 85.5; H, 8.07; $C_{15}H_{17}N$ requires: C, 85.3; H, 8.05%; ν_{\max} 1370 ($-\text{CH}_3$), 745 (four adjacent H), 857 (two adjacent H) and 885 cm^{-1} (one isolated H); λ_{\max} 237 mu (Intense) and 285 mu.

1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-2,4-dimethyl-N-benzoyl-5,6-benzoquinoline (III): 1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-2,4-dimethyl-5,6-benzoquinoline (1 g; 1 mol) and NaOH (0.25 g; 1.3 mol) were taken up in water (4 ml) and slightly warmed. The mixture was then allowed to cool and benzoyl chloride (0.7 g) added and shaken vigorously. Semisolid mass separated, a few of drops sodium hydroxide solution added and shaken again. The solid filtered, washed and recrystallised from alcohol; fine silky needles (0.80 g), m.p. 164-65°, insoluble in petroleum ether but soluble in methanol and chloroform. Found: C, 83.56; H, 6.12; $C_{22}H_{21}NO$ requires: C, 83.80; H, 6.60%; ν_{\max} 1390 ($-\text{CH}_3$), 1650 ($=\text{N}-\text{C}=\text{O}$), 748 (four adjacent H), 828 (two adjacent H) and 865 cm^{-1} (Isolated H); λ_{\max} 226 mu (Intense), 260 mu, 280 mu and 300 mu.

2-Amino-1-naphthoic acid (IV): 1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-2,4-dimethyl-N-benzoyl-5,6-benzoquinoline (III) (0.3 g) was dissolved in acetone (50 ml) and cooled to 2°. Finely powdered potassium permanganate (0.5 g) was added to it in portions with stirring. The mixture was allowed to stand for 48 hrs at room temperature. The solid was filtered washed with acetone and suspended in alcohol (35 ml). Moderately strong H_2SO_4 (1.2 ml, 1:1) was added, the mixture shaken and allowed to stand for

2 hrs. The solid residue was filtered, the filtrate evaporated and refluxed with dil. H_2SO_4 (25 ml) for 4 hrs. The turbid solution thus obtained was extracted with ether to remove benzoic acid. The aqueous layer was neutralised with Na_2CO_3 . The separated dirty mass was washed with water dried and recrystallised from alcohol (0.07 g) m.p. 128-29°. It gave positive test for $-\text{NH}_2$ and $-\text{COOH}$ groups. It is insoluble in petroleum ether and soluble in chloroform and ethanol.

1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-2,4-dimethyl-6,7-benzoquinoline (VI): was prepared according to the procedure⁶; m. p. 57-58°, Found: C, 84.52; H, 8.14; $C_{15}H_{17}N$ requires: C, 84.26; H, 8.11%; ν_{\max} 1372 ($-\text{CH}_3$), 740 (four adjacent H), and 873 cm^{-1} (Isolated H-atoms); λ_{\max} 245 mu (Intense) and 275 mu.

1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-2,4-dimethyl-N-benzoyl-6,7-benzoquinoline (VII): was prepared according to the procedure⁶, m. p. 110°, Found: C, 83.82; H, 6.60; $C_{22}H_{21}NO$ requires: C, 83.80; H, 6.55%; ν_{\max} 1379 ($-\text{CH}_3$), 1689 ($=\text{N}-\text{C}=\text{O}$), 750 (four adjacent H) and 880 cm^{-1} (Isolated H-atom); λ_{\max} 250 mu, 260 mu (Intense).

2-Amino-3-naphthoic acid (VIII): was prepared according to the procedure⁶, m. p. 213-14°.

Discussion

In 1885 Reed³ reported that a benzoquinoline (m. p. 126-127°) was obtained by Doebner-Von Miller reaction from paraldehyde, acetone and 2-naphthyl amine. This base is known as Reed's base. On the other hand Combes⁴ reported in 1888 that the reaction between 2-naphthylamine and acetylacetone gave a base $C_{15}H_{13}N$ (m. p. 66-67°) known as Combes' base. Johnson and Mathews⁵ suggested angular structure for Reed's base (I) and linear structure of Combes' base (V) based on the study of uv absorption spectra only.

We have carried out extensive studies on Reed's base¹ and conclusively proved that this base has angular structure. The Reed's base was reduced to 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-2,4-dimethyl-5,6-benzoquinoline (II) m.p. 109-10° with tin and hydrochloric acid^{5,6}, which was converted into 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-2,4-dimethyl-N-benzoyl-5,6-benzoquinoline (III) m. p.

(I)

(V)

164-65° by Baumann and Schotten reaction. 1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-2,4-dimethyl-N-benzoyl-5,6-benzoquinoline (III) was degraded by oxidation with potassium permanganate in acetone solution. The product of oxidation was neutralised with Na_2CO_3 and left overnight. The deposited dirty white solid recrystallised from alcohol gave colourless crystals of 2-amino-1-naphthoic acid^{7,8} (IV) m.p. 128-29°.

(IV)

Similarly 2,4-dimethyl-6,7-benzoquinoline was reduced to 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-2,4-dimethyl-6,7-benzoquinoline (VI) m.p. 57-58°, which was converted into 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-2,4-dimethyl-N-benzoyl-6,7-benzoquinoline (VII) m. p. 110° and this on oxidative degradation gave 2-amino-3-naphthoic acid⁹ (VIII) m.p. 213-14° by the methods described in the literature⁶.

(VIII)

The degradation of Reed's base to 2-amino-1-naphthoic acid reveals that in the formation of Reed's base ring closure at C_1 of naphthalene ring has taken place i.e., Reed's base has angular structure. While the degradation of Combes' base to 2-amino-3-naphthoic acid clearly indicates that C_3 of naphthalene ring is involved in new ring closure i.e., Combes' base has linear structure.

IR spectra: The ir spectral data of compounds (I) to (VIII) are given in Table I.

The presence of aromatic ring is best recognised by the presence of $=\text{C}-\text{H}$ stretching vibration near 3225 cm^{-1} to 3025 cm^{-1} , in compounds I to VIII and $-\text{C}=\text{C}-$ vibration in the region $1500-1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

TABLE-1

Comp I	Comp II	Comp III	Comp IV	Comp V	Comp VI	Comp VII	Comp VIII
3025	3290	3225	3430	3050	3280	3100	3420
2928			3080				3090
1588 vs	1625 vs	1650 vs	1680	1625	1629	1720	1680 vs
1550	1600 s	1598	1580	1580	1590	1625	1588
1370 s	1370	1390	1320	1362	1396	1379	1380
870 vs	865 s	865 s		890 s	860 vs	880	
850	857	828 vs	830	870	870	862	865
840	848			824		850	
750 vs	745 vs	748 vs	745 vs	740	745	750	
				722	720	725	722

According to Colthop¹⁰, the presence of bands in the region 1625 cm^{-1} to 1525 cm^{-1} shows aromatic character of the above compounds. A very strong band at 1650 cm^{-1} to 1689 cm^{-1} in compounds (III) and (VII) shows the presence of $=\text{N}-\text{C}=\text{O}$ group in them. The compounds (I), (II), (III), (V), (VI) and (VII) show bands at $1390-1360\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to presence of methyl group in them. In all compounds, there are four adjacent H-atoms which are confirmed¹¹ as these compounds have bands in the region $720-750\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Strong bands in the region $850-828\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are due to two adjacent H-atoms in compounds (I), (II), (III) and (IV) but these bands are absent in compounds (V), (VI), (VII) and (VIII) due to the absence of two adjacent H-atoms in them.

Absence of these bands may be taken as a proof of anthracene type of structure of the derivatives of Combes' base and presence of these bands may be taken as a proof of phenanthrene type of structure of the derivative of Reed's base.

The compounds I to III and V to VIII show strong bands in the region 885 to 862 cm^{-1} due to isolated H-atoms. The presence of isolated H-atoms in these compounds confirm the presence of two methyl groups in them.

One of the fundamental differences between Reed's base and Combes' base is that while the Reed's base contains 4-adjacent H-atoms, two adjacent H-atoms and one isolated H-atoms in the rings, the Combes' base contains 4-adjacent H-atoms, three isolated H-atoms but no two adjacent H-atoms in the rings.

The structure of Reed's base and Combes' base is further confirmed as these compounds on degradation gives 2-amino-1-naphthoic acid (IV) and 2-amino-3-naphthoic acid (VIII). The compounds (IV) and (VIII) show strong bands at 3430 cm^{-1} and 3420 cm^{-1} due to presence of $-\text{NH}_2$ group and bands at 1680 cm^{-1} due to presence of carbonyl group of carboxylic acid in them.

UV spectra: In anthracene and phenanthrene derivatives¹²⁻¹⁴ the band positions are near about the same but there is remarkable difference in the nature of absorption. In anthracene, the intensity of absorption increases with increasing wave length while in phenanthrene and its derivatives, the intensity of absorption decreases with increasing wave length.

The electronic spectra of 2,4-dimethyl-5,6-benzoquinoline and 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-N-benzoyl-5,6-benzoquinoline shows that the intensity of absorption increases with increase in wave length but opposite is the fact for 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-6,7-benzoquinoline and 1,2,3,4-N-benzoyl-6,7-benzoquinoline.

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References

1. PREM NARAYAN SINGH and NITYANAND SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, **14B**, 973.
2. W. S. JOHNSON and F. J. MATHEWS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 210.
3. J. HASTING REED, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1885, **32**, 630.
4. COMBES, *Compt. Rend.*, 1888, **106**, 1586.
5. V. BRAUN and GRUBER, *Ber.*, 1922, **55**, 1710.
6. NITYANAND SINGH and A. B. LAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 972.
7. *Chem. Abs.*, 1927, **21**, 2477.
8. FRIEDLANDER, LITTNER, *Ber.*, 1915, **48**, 328.
9. *Chem. Abs.*, 1933, **27**, 3343.
10. COLTHOP, *J. Opt. Soc. Am.*, 1950, **40**, 3979.
11. CANNON and SUTHERLAND, *Spectro Chim. Acta*, 1951, **4**, 373.
12. L. LANG, "Absorption Spectra", Hungarian Academy of Science, Budapest, 1961, Vol. I, p. 205, 219, 227.
13. L. LANG, "Absorption Spectra", Hungarian Academy of Science, Budapest, 1961, Vol. II, p. 293, 295, 297, 299.
14. JOHN D. ROBERTS and MARZORIE C. CASERIO, "Modern Organic Chemistry", W. A. Benjamin, Inc., 1967, p. 537.